

**Review of Process and Substance of
Undergraduate Curriculum Review
in two SPHEIR Projects
in Sierra Leone and Kenya**

– Final Report on AQHEd-SL –

21 February 2020

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2. Introduction

Pæradigms LLC was contracted in December 2019 to review the process and substance of the curriculum review (CR) of two projects that are part of the Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education Innovation and Reform (SPHEIR) : (1) “Assuring Quality Higher Education in Sierra Leone” (AQHEd-SL – see separate report) and (2) “Transformation of Pharmacy and Chemistry Degree Provision in Kenya” (K-N). **This report presents the results of the review on (1), i.e. AQHEd-SL.**

The results of this review are to inform the Mid-point Review (MPR), which was part of the original project design. While the projects aim goes well beyond CR and involves elements such as capacity building and outreach, CR remains at the very heart of the project and therefore is considered *conditio sine qua non* for the overall success of the project.

This final report presents the results of analysis of secondary data (project documentation provided by the SPHEIR fund manager (FM)) as well as primary data (interviews and field observations carried out in January 2020).

After this introduction (2) and the following methodological considerations (3), this final report summarizes the background and the fundamental design of the project (4) and the overall aims regarding CR (5). It then traces the actual structures for CR and the CR activities as of January 2020 (6) and moves on to the substances of CR (7) before evaluating both (6) and (7) in light of the original aims (5) in section (8). The report concludes with some additional observations and considerations (9).

3. Methodology

The evaluation draws both from secondary and primary project data. The secondary data was made available by the fund manager (FM). The wide range of information included:

- Application and grant stage 1 (GS1) documents
- Monitoring and evaluation (MEL) documents and reports
- Mid-point review (MPR) documents
- Quarterly reports (until Sep 2019, Q11)

The primary data was generated during the last two weeks of January 2020 on a five-day field trip to Sierra Leone (27-31 January 2020). The data is based on a total of 21 semi-structured, in-depth interviews with AQHEd-SL staff, partners, their constituencies and relevant stakeholders (for details see appendix 10.3). The interviews were organized in form of one-to-one sessions or in small groups (focus-group style) face-to-face and typically lasted between 45 and 60 minutes. The picture was completed by several in-depth conversations with BC staff. Whenever possible, the findings were validated through the triangulation method, i.e. several methods and sources were used to cross-verify the data (e.g. quarterly report, interview, observation). The constant comparison between the different sources did not only allow for data validation, but also for new themes and patterns to emerge.

4. Background and fundamental design of the project

The fundamental task of AQHEd-SL is to achieve transformational change in the HE system of Sierra Leone. The project was based on an initial **consortium of nine partners**: Three Sierra Leonian Universities (University of Sierra Leone (USL), Njala University (NU), and The University of Makeni (UniMak)), two external universities (King’s College London (KCL) and the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign (UIUC)), a national regulatory body (Tertiary Education Commission (TEC)), a national professional body (Sierra Leone Institute of Engineers (SLIE)), a national civil society organisation (The 50/50 Group), and an international higher education development agency (International Network for the Availability of Scientific Publications (INASP)).

USL serves as lead partner for the entire project; KCL serves as central fund manager (with a core competence in Monitoring and Evaluation (MEL)). The project is run by a project management board (PMB; located at USL) and a Project Coordinating Unit (as a joint USL-KCL body). The project was originally fundamentally structured by **three core work packages** (WPs). Corresponding to these work packages are three technical working groups (TWGs) – each chaired by one “lead institution”. The work packages/TWGs are: (1) Stakeholder Engagement, (2) Quality Management Systems and (3) Integration of outcome-based education (OBE). Relevant for the core of the CR process is primarily WP/TWG 3, but there are interconnections to WP1 (because stakeholders are to be integrated in CR) and WP/TWG2 (because curricula are also subject to quality management, e.g. by accreditation). **WP/TWG3 is lead by Njala University (NU)**. While NU is leading WP3 as a whole, four topical Clusters have been devised across different subject areas and different institutions serve as anchors for these clusters:

Cluster	Anchor	Ext. Partner
Health	USL – College of Medicine and Allied Health Sciences (COMAHS)	KCL
STEM	USL – Fourah Bay College (FBC)	SLIE
Agriculture	Njala University	UIUC
Management	University of Makeni	UIUC

Note: The original title of cluster 4, “economics and business” was eventually narrowed down to “management”.

The task of these anchor institutions is to oversee CR process, implementation, and “waterfalling” (to other institutions) for one program within the selected field (selected by the respective cluster) for each of two rounds of CR.

In the practical work of the project, the organizational distinction between the work packages proved to be somewhat artificial and lead to a duplication of efforts and a lack of coordination. Following a “consolidation process” in March 2019, the work package structure was thus de-emphasized; the fundamental tasks from these work packages, however, remained the same while being closer integrated with the work of the Clusters, which de facto now form the core working units of the project. QA, however, still plays a somewhat different role in this regard, as this has overarching characteristics and is coordinated via the TEC (its mandate spanning all HEIs in Sierra Leone).

5. Overall CR Aims and relevant planned activities up to MPR

a) The **overall aims** of AQHEd-SL can be summarized as follows: Inducing transformative change in the Sierra Leonean HEI system; in particular the introduction of high quality outcome-based education (OBE) tailored to actual labor-market demand. Central to this endeavor are “strategic” curriculum reform (CR) and implementation, including significant stakeholder input, staff capacity building, and the introduction of innovative teaching and learning systems.

b) The **specific, directly CR-oriented aims** can be summarized as follows: Development, and implementation of 2 x 4 = 8 curricula from four chosen thematic fields (health, STEM, agriculture, and management) in two consecutive rounds, where

- “development” includes extensive stakeholder input (WP1) in order to tailor the curricula to actual labor market demand, where
- “implementation” refers to the roll-out of the first set of four revised curricula at the AQHEd-SL institutions including (teaching and administrative) staff training and the introduction of innovative teaching methods, and where
- “waterfalling” refers to the roll-out of a second set of four revised curricula) at the four other HEIs in Sierra Leone (Ernest Bai Koroma University of Science and Technology (EBKUST); Milton Margai College of Education and Technology (MMCET); Freetown Teacher’s College (FTC) and Eastern Polytechnic Kenema (EPK)). These institutions were initially not part of the AQHEd-SL-consortium, but are now full project partners.

In addition, the entire process is supposed to lead to standardized, consensual, high-quality blueprints for curriculum reform procedures that ensure a further universalization of this approach across Sierra Leone HEIs resulting in truly transformational change.

c) The relevant **concrete activities** for the CR process are to be found chiefly in the work plan for the WPs 1 & 3 (Annex A to the Grant Agreement). Most significant are the following:

#	Planned Activity	WP	WP-lead	Project Output	Planned for ¹
01	Employer Focus Panels/Employer Engagement Strategy	1	UniMak	1	Q05
02	Skills Development Network/Sector Skills Councils	1	UniMak	1	Q06 – Q08 Q10 – Q12
03	Decision on four initial programs for CR	3	NU + CA	4	Q05
04	16 3-day curriculum revision workshops (4 per Cluster) - Content, Methodology, Assessment, LMS - Development of Curriculum Revision Templates	3	NU + CA	4	Q06 – Q12
05	Validation/Ratification of revised curricula	3	NU + CA	4	Q09
06	Curricula Implementation Planning/Staff Training	3	NU + CA	4	Q09 – Q10
07	Curricula Roll-Out	3	NU + CA	4	Q11 – Q12
08	Waterfalling Process (1 anchor – 1 beneficiary)	3	NU + CA	4	Q08 – Q12

¹ For naming conventions see Annex 6.1.

Note 1: CA = Thematic Cluster Anchors (USL-COMAHS, USL-FBC, NU, UniMAK); see above

Note 2: Following the project consolidation workshop in March 2019 new timeframes and milestones were defined. The fundamental line-up of CR activities, however, remained largely unchanged.

d) As part of the **project-internal MEL**, a set of indicators was devised for both outcomes and outputs of the project. The *outcome indicators* largely correspond the general project aims outlined above. Two are of particular relevance for the CR process at MPR: (1) Stakeholders are/were actively involved in CR at SL's HEIs (Outcome 1 – Indicators 1 & 2); (2) actual curricula and course delivery have changed (Outcome 1 – Indicator 3). The *output indicators* are tailored to the work plan in Annex A. In the context of CR, the indicators for outputs 1 and 4 are of particular relevance (see table above). For Output 1 they focus on the successful establishment of the Skills Development Network (SDN) (with broad participations of employers/stakeholders and HEI). For Output 4 they focus on the number of revised curricula and their implementation. MEL-data is thus of particular interest with regard to (a) stakeholder/employer integration and (b) actual curriculum revision and roll-out.

6. Actual Structures and Processes of CR (as of Jan 2020)

6.1 Governance and Team Structure

The most important executive structure of the project is the **project coordination unit (PCU)**, operating out of USL. Following the consolidation phase in March 2019, the PCU was restructured. Most significant was the appointment of a full-time project director, the addition of two advisors for CR and QA respectively, and the employment of two project officers (POs). Aside from other duties (such as the organization of PITF meetings), these POs handle two anchor institutions/Clusters each. With these measures, the organizational capabilities of the PCU were significantly strengthened. Interview partners were united in their appraisal for the post-consolidation work of the PCU as a whole and, in particular, the work of the project director and the POs (I03-SL, I04-SL, I05-SL, I08-SL, I13-SL, I16-SL). Universal feedback was that the “new” PCU has created a core focal point that supports (and pushes) structured work processes in all Clusters.

Overall, the project has seen a significant amount of **staff turnover** in various positions – ranging from DVCs in different HEIs via a number of Cluster leads (Management, Agriculture) to staff in accounting and MEL. It is important to note that this staff turnover is mostly beyond the control of AQHEd-SL. In the context of the HE system of Sierra Leone, it is not uncommon that especially senior staff either is moved (because of political considerations; see below) or moves in order to secure more attractive positions. However, the turnover as such has not remained without consequences and the project continues to suffer from issues such as loss of institutional memory, repeated learning phases, delays because of communication problems, etc.

6.2 Stakeholder Engagement (corresponding activities #01 and #02)

Stakeholder Engagement was originally considered a separate work package (WP1). Initial activities in 2018 included four employer “focus panels” (Jun 2018); the development of employer questionnaires (Jul 2018); a launch event for the “skills development network” (Sep 2018). Cluster specific stakeholder activities took the form of “sector skills council” meetings (Fall 2018). However, the success of these activities was rather mixed. Stakeholder themselves saw it as “artificially detached” from CR (I16-SL, I21-SL) and the actual turnout varied considerably (with one stakeholder event in the Management cluster having to be cancelled). As sketched before, the separation of stakeholder and CR activities was seen as artificial; the SSCs were considered redundant. After the consolidation process **stakeholder activities were closely integrated into CR**; the originally intended “sector skills councils” (SSC) do not really exist as such. Overall stakeholder activities have taken three main forms (I03-SL): (1) Group discussions/workshops with stakeholders, (2) surveys/questionnaires and/or individual interviews, (3) integration of stakeholders into CR meetings. (Whatsapp groups – generally very common in SL – have turned out to be a powerful tool of stakeholder involvement.) By now, activities have moved away from (1) and more in the direction of (3) with occasional instances of (2). Most active have been government institutions (ministries, agencies) and businesses (in this order) -- followed by broader university staff.

The involvement of NGOs and students is still rather the exception than the rule. However, there is by now a fairly stable group of stakeholders (in each cluster) that is continuously integrated into the respective CR activities and has clearly attained ownership of the process (I19-SL, I20-SL, I21-SL). This has become so strong, that in the case of CR in pharmacy – where activities have not reached the intensity of the other Clusters (see sec. 4.3.3) – a stakeholder intends to push the Cluster into (more) action (I21-SL).

All Clusters demonstrate a **rather comprehensive line-up of stakeholder involvement**; spanning all three sectors with a considerable bias towards public institutions. This, however, can be seen as plausible based on the de facto employment situation in SL.

Cluster	Public	Business	3rd Sector
STEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Information and Communication (MIC) • Ministry of Energy (MOE) • National Telecommunications Commission (NATCOM) • Electricity Distribution and Supply Authority (EDSA) • Electricity Generation & Transmission Authority (EGTC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SierraTel (public) • Orange Mobile • SL Cement Corporation (LEOCEM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SL Institution of Engineers (SLIE)
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Finance • Public Service Commission • Audit Service SL (ASSL) • Human Resource Management Office (HRMO) • National Social Security and Insurance Trust (NASSIT) • National Revenue Agency (NRA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SL Association of Commercial Banks • KPMG/BakerTilly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institute of Chartered Accountants of SL • Students
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enterprise Development Services Ltd. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action Against Hunger (ACF) • BRAC

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Agriculture Forestry and Food Security • National Minerals Agency SL Chamber for Agribusiness Development (SLeCAD) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students
Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Health and Sanitation (MOHS) • Health Service Commission • Pharmacy Board SL • National Medicines Supply Agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmacy Business Association 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinton Health Access Initiative (CHAI) • Pharmaceutical Society SL • Young Pharmacists Group

(Source: PS-SL; differentiation by sector GWD; student involvement at Njala University could not be verified; I18-SL)

Future plans for stakeholder engagement focus on making it permanent and even more comprehensive. This could include tying SPHEIR-stakeholders to the university career offices, the organization of sector-specific careers fairs, networking events, etc. (I03-SL).

6.3 Curriculum Review Process

6.3.1 Selection of Programs (corresponding activity #03)

As early as June 2018, all four Clusters had been formed and all of them had selected programs for CR – summarized in the following table:

Cluster	Program	Anchor
STEM	BSc in Electrical & Electronic Engineering (BEENG)	USL – FBC
Management	BSc in Accounting & Finance	UniMak
Agriculture	BSc in Agriculture (General)	Njala U
Health	Diploma in Pharmacy; later: B Pharm	USL – COMAHS

However, in the case of the pharmacy cluster, the program subject to CR was eventually changed from a (3-year) diploma in pharmacy to a (5-year) B Pharm in Spring 2019. This change happened primarily because of the appointment of a new Deputy Vice-Chancellor (DVC) at COMAHS towards the end of 2018. Originally, the diploma was chosen because it had never been reviewed – contrary to the B Pharm that had already undergone CR in 2014 (see “pre-history” sec 4.5.3 below) – and because it was considered rather meaningful to increase the educational standards for pharmacy technicians (i.e. the typical job after a Diploma in pharmacy). However, while being equally committed to the SPHEIRS process as a whole, the new DVC at COMAHS argued that (a) the comprehensive character of the CR effort was out of proportion with the relevance and the overall academic level of the diploma and (b) COMAHS should not undergo this process on a lower level than the other Clusters (I08-SL, I09-SL). This was compatible to the political intention publicly stated by the Minister of Education, according to which universities (such as USL, of which COMAHS is a part) should focus on degree programs while TVET institutions should focus on programs below the BA-level. (There is also the rumor that the DVC’s wife is a holder of a Pharma Diploma and has an active interest in taking a (renewed) B Pharm (I04-SL).) Whatever the ultimate reason, the DVC insisted on his decision despite

opposition from stakeholders who argued that the (just reviewed) B Pharm should eventually rather undergo a development in the direction of a Pharm D in order to match the general tendency towards “cooperation among equals” between medical doctors and pharmacists. From this perspective, it was also particularly meaningful to upgrade the Diploma. However, the DVC (himself an MD) stood by his decision. The result was a considerable delay so that the CR proper in Pharmacy started in earnest only after the consolidation phase in about May 2019.

6.3.2 CR proper (corresponding activities #04, #05, #06 and #07)

As agreed by all Clusters, the CR process has four essential steps: (1) Overall structure review and module identification (in conjunction with stakeholder involvement), (2) module re-design, (3) validation/ratification by the appropriate institutional bodies, and (4) roll-out and implementation (i.e. actual teaching).

All Clusters have found a particular way to speed up (3) – and thus also (4): The **ratification process** usually involves the faculty board, the academic Senate, sometimes a CR committee of the Senate, the Senate again, and ultimately the TEC. However, all Clusters have started to distinguish between “major revisions” (which leads to the program having to be accepted by the TEC) and “minor revisions” for which an intra-university ratification is sufficient, sometimes – depending on the nature of the revisions – only by the faculty board. A significant part of the revisions were deemed “minor” in order to speed up the process and allow for a faster roll-out. There is no clear unified standard for what constitutes a “minor” or a “major” revision – sometimes e.g. in the BEENG program an entire redrafting of a syllabus was deemed a “minor change” (I05-SL). It thus appears that Clusters have found a rather pragmatic way of handling ratification. As long as the project enjoys the full support of the relevant Senate members and the TEC, it seems to be universally accepted to do a series of “minor revisions” concluding in a universal ratification on the TEC level only when a significant part of the curriculum is already being implemented. However, the Clusters’ progress is uneven:

Work in the **STEM Cluster** is co-ordinated by USL -- FCB as anchor institution. The 5-year BSc in electrical engineering has a total 50 modules. Of these 38 were selected for revision; 22 for major revisions, 16 for minor revision. The respective course instructors have the lead for the CR of “their” modules. The courses to be revised are grouped content-wise and stakeholder involvement then proceeds within these groups. Three CR workshops have already taken place; the first one in Nov 2018. As a result, as of Jan 2020, all 16 minor revisions are completed and approved by the department; 10 of these are already being rolled-out; the other six will be rolled out in March 2020. For 2020, three more CR workshops are scheduled; as a result, all 22 modules under “major revision” are to be completed by Oct 2020. For these a full ratification process will have to happen, but it is expected to take not more than three months, so that full roll-out can be expected the latest by Mar 2021 (semester start). (myr19, I04-SL, I05-SL).

The **Management Cluster** is co-ordinated by the University of Makeni (UniMak); a private (catholic) university, for which a Bishop serves as Chancellor. Initially, processes in this Cluster were slow to start; an early stakeholder event had to be cancelled for lack of interest. However, after the consolidation process things started moving fast. Chosen was a 5-year BSc in Accounting & Finance with a total of 50 teaching modules, ALL of which were chosen for review. Since March 2019 various stakeholder meetings have taken place (often as interviews in stakeholders’ offices). As of January

2020 and based on four CR workshops, 14 modules have been reviewed and are already being rolled-out. 12 more are currently under review and will be rolled-out in March this year (semester start). Another batch of 12 will be rolled-out with the beginning of the semester in Oct, and the final batch of 12 by March 2021. (myr19, I12-SL)

Njala University (NU) is responsible for the **Agriculture Cluster**. At NU, things were slow to start. There were severe deficiencies in financial management capacity – to the extent that a person from KCL was seconded there; participation in Cluster events was sub-standard. However, now NU has decided to review the complete 5-year BSc in General Agriculture and all of its 43 modules. Four CR workshops have been held; six more are planned until mid-2021. In the process, the 10 first semester modules have been compressed into seven, all of which are currently being rolled out. Five 2nd semester modules are currently under review and are scheduled to be rolled out in March 2020. The third semester courses are to be rolled out by Oct 2020; the final batch in 2021. (myr19, I12-SL)

In comparison, activities in the **Health Cluster** are rather moderate. Following the switch from the 3-year Diploma to the 5-year B Pharm the stakeholder process (that had already taken place in 2018) had to be started anew in May 2019 (!), because the relevant stakeholder input varies significantly between the two degrees as they lead to different employment scenarios (“pharmaceutical technician” versus “pharmacist”). A fresh round of stakeholder meetings has been held, but they have resulted in the choice of only 9-10 “critical” modules for revision – out of the 50 total modules of the B Pharm. (Interviewees gave differing information about the number of modules selected for CR.) Apparently, for none of these 9-10 CR is complete; none is currently rolled-out. Plans are now to proceed with CR in parallel to the waterfaling institution (EBKUST; see below) in order to reach the (rather modest goals) by the end of the project’s lifetime (I08-SL, I09-SL).

6.3.3 Teaching Methodology and Teaching Assessment (corresponding activity #06)

Academic staff from all Clusters has participated in a series of workshops of cross-cutting topics in Feb and May 2019, facilitated by external partners such as the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign (UIUC), the International Network for the Availability of Scientific Publications (INASP) and the 50/50 Group. The workshops focused in particular on: **Pedagogy, Critical Thinking, Problem-Solving, Teaching Assessment and gender sensitivity.**

6.3.4 Waterfaling (corresponding activity #08)

From the project’s inception, each of the anchor institutions is cooperating with a “waterfaling institution” in order to extend the range of the project’s activities and mentor CR processes at the respective “waterfaling partner”. All interviewees confirmed that the waterfaling institutions have been participating as equals in all project activities from its inception (stakeholder workshops, training workshops, CR workshops, consolidation workshop etc). All waterfaling institutions have also chosen programs for CR:

Cluster	Program	Anchor	Waterfalling Institution
STEM	BSc in Civil Engineering	USL – FCB	Eastern Polytechnic (EP)
Management	BSc in Business Administration	UniMak	Freetown Teacher’s College (FTC)
Agriculture	BSc in Agriculture (General)	Njala U	Milton Margai College of Education and Technology (MMCET)
Health	BSc in Public Health	USL – COMAHS	Ernest Bai Koroma University of Science and Technology (EBKUST)

For most Clusters, the chosen programs correspond the ones at the anchor institutions in that they are within the same disciplinary field, but have a slightly different focus (“Civil Engineering” at EP versus “Electrical Engineering” at UCL-FCB; “Business Administration” at MMCET versus “Accounting and Finance” at UniMak; “Public Health” at EBKUST versus “Pharmacy” at USL-COMAHS). In the case of Agriculture, the program is identical between Njala University and MMCET. In fact staff from Njala University serve as external examiners for MMCET and are vetting the respective program. In this particular case, waterfalling will refer simply to the takeover of the NU program (complemented by the respective staff training).

The advantage of this approach lies in the close disciplinary ties between the staff members who see themselves as colleagues and sometimes have studied together. The disadvantage lies in the fact that under transformative perspective the disciplinary correspondence limits the spread of the CR process across different faculties.

6.3.5 Development of CR templates (corresponding activity #04)

Following one of the original intentions of the project, a general **CR template document** was produced (I02-SL, I04-SL, I11-SL). The process was somewhat delayed (due to management and coordination deficiencies), but by September 2019 a writing group of seven had completed the document. By now (Jan 2020) it has been validated in a stakeholder meeting (cutting across all four Clusters) and all Academic Senates of the anchor institutions have formally approved it. The respective process at the waterfalling institutions is still pending. Also, a number of training workshops on the template have already held, more are scheduled, specifically for the waterfalling institutions. The template consists of two core documents:

- “Overview of Curriculum Review Process and Curriculum Review Templates” (Vol .1)
- “Analysis of Curriculum Mapping Data” (Vol. 2)

7. Substance of Curriculum Review

7.1 CR proper

For the **STEM Cluster** stakeholder feedback focused on critical skills, such as “computer literacy”, practical and applied skills and competences, and soft skills such as communication and presentation skills. Examples for CR in the BEENG that responded to these demands include: (1) The introduction of a course on “computing”, (2) “Instrumentation” instead of “Applied Mechanics”, (3) “Software Engineering” as a mandatory course, (4) “Electromagnetic Waves” instead of the (basic physics) course on “Electrical Fields”, (5) an elective on “Computer technology” and “satellite communication”, (6) the introduction of modern programming languages (such as C++) in various courses, (7) the introduction of industrial visits, (8) introduction of simulation software for high-voltage engineering (for which there is no lab in existence in SL).

Stakeholder involved in the **Management Cluster** focused on deficits in basic skills (computer skills, team work, presentation skills, numerical interpretation) and the huge gap between theory and practical application. Furthermore they pointed out that graduates had little or no mindset of entrepreneurship (the writing of business plans; credit and finance, etc). In response, the CR team has reduced the number of credit points, reduced redundancies, merged some modules and unified terminology across modules in order to make room for practical applications and case studies. Also, it has introduced a standardized teaching format by means of which the above skills can be integrated in most courses.

In the **Agriculture Cluster**, stakeholders mostly focused on the employers perspective and pointed out that graduates lacked basic skills such as report writing; basic calculations; language capabilities ,etc. It transpired from the interviews (I13-SL, I14-SL, I15-SL, I18-SL) that actual changes so far are primarily based on the teaching methodology and assessment workshops. Their application, however, seems to be rather widespread (including the waterfalling institution, I15-SL) and very popular with students (I18-SL).

In the **Health Cluster**, stakeholder feedback also focused on ICT-skills and soft skills, but also the training on templates of the West African Pharmaceutical Society as well as general research skills and lab skills and a strengthening of the community-based approach. Not much information could be gathered about the actual CR changes because the process has just started. The one example given for a concrete change (moving “Pharmaceutics I” from Sem. 3 to Sem. 1) raises doubts about the depth of the intended revisions. However, it was mentioned in multiple interviews (I08-SL, I09-SL, I10-SL) that the workshops on teaching methodology were particularly useful and could be immediately applied e.g. introducing the problem-solving approach for patient scenarios (instead of classical teaching on therapeutical approaches).

7.2 Teaching and Assessment Methodology

Cross-cutting capacity building was implemented by a series of workshop on specific topics, in particular Pedagogy, Critical Thinking, Problem-Solving, Teaching Assessments and Gender

Sensitivity. While an independent evaluation of the workshops was not possible (workshop material was not available; participant observation not possible), it is noteworthy that interviewees mentioned time and again that these workshops were extremely useful (I05-SL, I07-SL, I08-SL, I10-SL, I13-SL, I14-SL).

The 50/50 group reported that their workshops were met with considerable interest and covered gender issues beyond CR such as campus policies, university policies, HR policies, etc. (I01-SL). The group concluded that a certain sensitivity to gender issues is, by now, widely internalized across the Clusters. However, openness towards gender issues was reportedly higher in pharmacy and management than in STEM and agriculture (which are considered “male” disciplines). The collaboration with UniMak was considered particularly fruitful because UniMak is significantly more flexible in adapting its policies than the public universities.

Concerning the **teaching oriented workshops**, it is noteworthy that the only student in the line-up of interviewees (I18-SL) from Njala University referred to the “new teaching methods” as a “game changer”. In this context, it is important to note that approaches taught in these workshops found application not only in the programs undergoing CR but also in general teaching in the respective institutions. They are thus a particularly important tool for transformative change in the sense of “inter-university spread” (see sec. 4.5.3 below).

7.3 CR Templates

The template documents that were developed (see above sec. 4.3.3.5) focus on the overall CR process (Vol. 1) as well as course level design (Vol. 2). Vol. 1 introduces a cyclical model of CR, and provides background considerations (among other things) on reasons and benefits of CR, degree-level expectations, and learning outcomes. Vol. 2 introduces the tool of curriculum mapping (mapping course-level learning outcomes against program level outcomes) and provides additional information on linking learning outcomes to assessment methods. The quality of these documents is high and they rely on (and quote) international standard references.

8. Evaluation

8.1 Structures and Processes

It transpires very clearly from the available data that the initial activities of the project in 2018 were slow to start, somewhat unfocused and incoherent. These activities also suffered from unclarity and capacity-deficits in project governance, management, organization, reporting and co-ordination across a rather large consortium. At the same time, this consortium was tasked with an intensity of cooperation hitherto unknown to SL (and unusual in other national contexts as well), and it was facing not least technical problems in a low-level development context (internet connectivity, power outages; difficult and time-consuming travels, low-capacity in financial management etc.).

After the consolidation process in spring 2019, however, activities have become significantly more focused and coherent across the board. By now, processes seem to be running much more smoothly. The re-structuring of the PMU was a full success, but could be tweaked further (see recommendations below). For CR, making “modules” the core unit-of analysis has significantly improved the hands-on work on the actual curricula. (Other positive trends are visible across various activities: from a clarification of institutional roles, via the filling of posts, to clearer reports and better documentation.)

However: All Clusters are facing challenging timelines now. The interview data for this report was collected parallel to a central project workshop, in which new milestones, timelines and Gantt-charts for all Clusters were compiled. The most important parts of these were reported in the information about Clusters’ CR activities (see sec. 4.3.3.2). No matter how these timelines look like, however, they are necessarily tight. Further delays will make it impossible to roll-out the reviewed curricula in the lifetime of the project. Time management will thus be now essential for the project’s overall success.

The Health Cluster poses a specific challenge. It is significantly lagging behind the other Clusters because of its late (and not entirely uncontested) switch of programs. Also, the scope of the planned activities seems to be so limited that it hardly amounts to comprehensive CR.

8.2 Substance of CR

For the **STEM and Management Clusters**, CR seems to be fully answering to stakeholders demands while comprehensively covering the respective curricula. Changes are deep and cover both topics as well as teaching methodology.

For the **Agriculture Cluster** the connection between stakeholder demands and actual topical changes in the curriculum is still less visible. However, the changes in teaching methodology are significant and have apparently already been spread widely – and with considerable success.

In the **Health Cluster** the scope of topical change seems to be even more limited than in agriculture. To a certain degree, however, this is not surprising given that (a) the B Pharm curriculum is – stronger than all the other curricula – based on classical teaching “canon” and that (b) the curriculum has just undergone CR in 2014. (From hindsight, the decision to switch seems to have been a rather bad call.) It seems thus unlikely that topical change can be easily expanded. However, it does seem feasible that stakeholder demands (templates, research skills, community-based approach) are fully considered. Similarly, the changes to teaching and assessment can be fully realized across the entire curriculum.

8.3 Transformational Effects

The overall goal of SPHEIR is to trigger transformational change, i.e. fundamental, systemic and sustainable improvements of HE in the respective target country. Given the rather limited immediate scope of CR of just $2 \times 4 = 8$ academic programs on the BA-level (and the limited timeframe of the

project), this can only be reached, if the CR process itself reaches a “critical mass” beyond which the process becomes self-sustained and the spread of CR continues beyond the life-time of the project.

This, in turn critically hinges on a number of conditions, processes, and “environmental factors”. *The* core condition is that **all relevant actors identify with the goals and methods of CR as introduced by SPHEIR**. In this regard the projects seems to exceptionally successful. All interviewees showed a remarkable enthusiasm about the goals of the project and displayed a **full “buy-in”**. It was reported multiple times that CR and innovations in teaching methodology met in the wider faculty with little resistance (if at all), and that the positive feedback from students as well as the political backing by VCs and DVCs made it easy to introduce the respective measures.

Process-wise, the sustainability of the project will have to rely on processes of Inter-University Diffusion and Intra-University Diffusion. **Inter-University Diffusion** is already a part of the project in the form of the “waterfalling process”. The scope of this process, however, does not cover all HEIs in SL yet. Instances of Inter-University Diffusion beyond the project were reported (I12-SL) but they are incidental so far. It is noteworthy in this regard that the SPHEIR project became the occasion of the formation of the SL-wide “Conference of VCs and Principals”, which can be used as a core platform for Inter-University Diffusion. (Note: The Conference has yet to hold its inaugural meeting.) However, given that the project already unites the most significant HEIs in SL, **Intra-University Diffusion** is probably even more important. Here the available evidence shows that some of these processes have already happened – mainly driven by curiosity and a certain “jealousy” of colleagues not involved in the project. However, it has to be noted that the existing instances of Intra-University Diffusion remain limited to diffusion *within faculties*. The spread across faculties has yet to organized. For both types of diffusion, the general template documents are of critical importance. They are easy to distribute and use and provide for a standardization of the process.

It should also be considered that there is a necessary connection between teaching at secondary and tertiary level (I11-SL). The rather sobering state of affairs in tertiary education in SL prior to SPHEIR mirrors the conditions in secondary education. It could thus be highly effective in terms of “**Vertical Diffusion**” to systematically integrate the departments of education in the project. It is to expected that successful CR and reform of teaching methodology there could have powerful knock-on effects on secondary education.

In order to evaluate the “environmental factors” relevant of the project, it is necessary to recall its **pre-history** (I04-SL, I11-SL, I16-SL). At least two years before the SPHEIR call there were already three relevant streams of activities (chiefly at USL): (1) Attempts at comprehensive CR in the Engineering Department of FCB, (2) an actual CR of the B Pharm at COMAHS, and (3) attempts to develop a QA policy for USL as a whole (originally kick started by the participation of individuals from USL und NU in a DAAD-sponsored QA-program in 2013). These three streams of activities came together with the SPHEIR call and were merged in writing the respective proposal. (In particular, it became clear during the proposal writing phase that QA could serve as a means to make CR change permanent and controlled.) Moreover, the SPHEIR call has helped to overcome the hitherto prevalent competitive atmosphere between the SL HEIs. Interviewees agreed that already the process of proposal writing has allowed for a new level of collaboration among the HEIs and a sense of community hat did not exist before. In a sense, the project has thus had transformational effects before it even started. What is more, it transpired from various interviews that SPHEIR has served as an enormously effective catalyst of change in SL HE that was “in the air” but never close to being realized on this scale. Particularly the Member of the PMB (I11-SL), the Cluster leads in Engineering, Management, and

Agriculture (I04-SL, I12-SL, I13-SL), the topical leads in stakeholder engagement and QA (I03-SL, I16-SL), as well as all interviewed stakeholders (I19-SL, I20-SL, I21-SL) showed a significant intrinsic motivation to make the changes permanent and continue CR and stakeholder engagement activities after the end of the lifetime of the project. It is noteworthy that not in all but in many cases, this intrinsic motivation is older than the project (and thus very likely to persist).

At the same time, it also is equally important to note that prior efforts at CR and HE reform had been – time and again – frustrated by **political interventions** (I04-SL, I11-SL). The reform of HE laws in 2005/6, which – among other things – have made the President of Sierra Leone Chancellor of the public universities, has opened the door to more and more political interference in HE. Most significant are politically motivated staff changes on the level of VCs, DVCs, and even Deans. These changes have repeatedly frustrated reform efforts, e.g. because the incoming managerial staff was not committed to the reform agenda, or may have even pushed his or her own agenda (potentially conflicting with the aims of the reform process). While from this perspective SPHEIR was a tremendous opportunity to trigger reform more independent of such influences (involving a large international donor), the project has also been affected by these tendencies – most notably in the Health Cluster at COMAHS (see above). The question thus becomes how the transformational effects can be hedged against potential future political interventions.

Finally, it has to be considered that the long-term success of SPHEIR will depend on the **continuing support by and the political independence of the TEC**. So far, the TEC and its rather strong president have fully supported SPHEIR – not least because the project has increased the relevance and visibility of a hitherto rather “orphaned” institution. At the same time, the TEC has managed to keep of the “political radar”.

9. Additional Considerations

Note: The following sections 9.1 and 9.2 go beyond the ToR of this report. They are thus not part of the formal findings but they are included with the intention of contributing additional ideas that might be helpful in the further development of the project.

9.1 Issues beyond CR

The main issue beyond CR that was mentioned multiple times in interviews (I02-SL, I12-SL, I13-SL, I16-SL) concerns MEL – with regard to both, substance and process. While by now the PCU and respective MEL staff is well-versed in the logic of the MEL-system, the decentralized units (and in particular the Clusters) are notoriously sloppy and slow in reporting and fulfilling the respective standards. Overall, the project has less a project with its activities than with properly reporting them. However, the issue also refers to the MEL-system as such. Particular points of criticism and suggestions include:

- MEL capacity should be built and maintained in all project subunits (anchors, waterfalling institutions)

- MEL Indicators were developed centrally with little regard for the situation on the ground. Instead MEL indicators should mirror the complexity of the project structure, and project content
- MEL indicators should reflect more substance than process and be based on comprehensive data collection (not least among teachers and students)
- There are synergies between project MEL and the QA module (which is also some kind of MEL), which should be fully realized

9.2 Recommendations for AQHEd-SL

1. **Further enhance the capacity of the PMU.** It is evident, that the post-consolidation reform of the PMU has significantly improved the overall management of the project. However, while the POs play a core role as full-time employees that drive the Cluster processes, there capacity is limited. Especially the need to “bridge” two different Clusters (at different physical locations) limits their effectiveness. It seems advisable to hire one PO for each Cluster and distribute cross-cutting tasks among them. Given the limited cost for these position, this seems to be a highly efficient measure to increase project effectiveness. The same applies to finance officers (who could be dispatched to anchor and waterfalling institutions). While the necessary funds are limited, the potential gain is significant.
2. **Take measures to limit staff turnover.** Staff turnover on all levels translates into delays and endangers project effectiveness. Some of these changes (such as the appointment of a new DVC) are beyond the project’s control. In other cases (in particular Cluster leads, functional unit leads and all staff on the project’s payroll), concrete measures should be taken to limit staff changes. This could include written commitments to serve as, say, Cluster lead until the end of the project’s lifetime and/or financial incentives (on lower levels).
3. **Consider a re-calibration of MEL.** The existing MEL scheme has been criticized above. It seems advisable to use the mid-point review to review the existing indicators with a number of specific goals: (1) Facilitate and unify the reporting lines and formats, (2) Re-calibrate the indicators towards substance (rather than process), (3) consider qualitative indicators that capture actual classroom activity, specifically: (4) consider on-site visits oriented towards qualitative evaluation of program implementation; (5) use synergies between existing QA-approaches and project-MEL.
4. **Make monitoring of Cluster timelines a core task of the PCU.** As outlined above, all Clusters now face very tight timelines. While it is certainly still possible, a close monitoring will be necessary to make Clusters meet their goals within the lifetime of the project.
5. **Actively intervene in the activities of the Health Cluster.** The Health Cluster is significantly lagging behind, both in the scope and in the timing of its activities. The goals for CR could be more ambitious than 9-10 modules, it should be closely matching stakeholder demand and the process needs to significantly speed up. In addition, changes to teaching methodology could be spread fully across the program. (Note: It is rather remarkable that this under-performing Cluster is the only one having an international partner directly connected to the subject area and present on-site.)

6. **Consider stakeholder involvement as broadly as possible.** While the existing stakeholder activities were comprehensive and successful with regard to CR, stakeholder involvement can go beyond this. In fact, stakeholder involvement can be considered for the entire “lifecycle” of a student at an HEI. It starts with stakeholder integration in student selection, can go on to co-teaching or guest lectures; pre-defined internship; final theses and research in cooperation with practice institutions and, obviously, systematic placements effort in cooperation with the respective career service units. Finally there is alumni work, which can feedback into CR (post graduation curriculum evaluation) as well as all other steps mentioned above.
7. **Consider drafting, distributing, training on and “politically marketing” existing and additional template documents.** Template documents such as the ones already developed for CR and QA are powerful tools for transformational effects. They can be widely distributed, provided free of charge, and define standards for all HEIs. They will gain particular traction if SPHEIR organized a number of **training workshops on these template** at various SL HEIs (even beyond the waterfalling institutions). If their reputation is high enough they could constitute a generally accepted “SPHEIR standard”; in an ideal case they could as such be **adopted by the TEC** and made mandatory for all SL HEIs. This latter step would require a political process (see recommendation 8) but is considered possible (I11-SL and, most significantly I16-SL). In order to maximize the potential all major SPHEIR activities could be translated in such template documents; more specifically:
 - (a) Comprehensive CR Handbook (uniting the existing documents)
 - (b) Practitioners’ Handbook for Best Practice in Teaching (including gender)
 - (c) Stakeholder Integration Handbook
 - (d) QA Handbook (already in existence; not reviewed)

Handbook (b) could be compiled based on contributions by the facilitators of the respective workshops (UIUC, INASP, 50/50); handbook (c) could be the stakeholder engagement lead (UniMak). The amount of extra effort would be rather marginal; the impact potentially very high. The TEC should be continuously involved in the process.

8. **Make intra- and inter-university diffusion a top priority.** While it seems rather likely that CR in the targeted institutions and programs will be successful, transformational effects across SL will critically hinge on the diffusion processes beyond the immediate institutional target group. To a certain extent this has already started – be it as “push process” by training non-consortium members on CR and teaching methodology, be it as “pull process” when documents were shared and used on the own initiative of “neighboring” programs or departments. However, in the remaining lifetime of the project, these processes could be more systematically centrally co-ordinated and given high priority. Systematic wide-spread training based on the “Handbooks” (see rec. 7) would be particularly effective in this regard.
9. **Consider strategic “2nd generation waterfalling” to departments of education for the purpose of “Vertical Diffusion”.** It was noted in a number of interviews (I02-SL, I04-SL, I11-SL) that the low teaching standards in Sierra Leonean HEIs was a reflection of the low teaching standards in secondary education which are “carried on” in the tertiary sector. Integrating the various departments of education at anchor and waterfalling institutions into SPHEIR (in particular with regard to teaching methodology) could thus have significant potential to spread the transformational change beyond the tertiary sector and is otherwise a “low hanging fruit”. The SL “Council of Principals” could also be eventually integrated.

10. **Significantly expand public outreach and communications for SPHEIR.** This recommendation has essentially two core functions: (1) to ease intra- and interuniversity diffusion of core SPHEIR concepts and ideas, and (2) create a positive public political climate towards SPHEIR itself as well as its ideas that could serve to hedge it against political interference. The respective efforts should specifically target “young” media, such as Internet-based social media (Facebook, Youtube-Clips with direct quotes from students etc.) and radio. It seems possible to actively integrate students in SPHEIR programs into this endeavor.
11. **Actively promote SPHEIR concepts in the political realm.** It might be helpful to actively advertise SPHEIR as well as its concepts and ideas in the political realm. This could also serve to protect SPHEIR from adverse political interference; create incentives for more institutions to “jump on the bandwagon”, generally support the intra- and inter-university diffusion process and work on and with the TEC for the adoption of the “handbooks” (see rec. 7).
12. **Consider complementary programs for “hardware support” (outside SPHEIR; possibly even outside DFID).** It is quite noteworthy in how many interviews it was mentioned that SPHEIR has achieved remarkable progress on the “soft side” of concepts, ideas, approaches, and tools, while the actual application of these is often significantly hampered by the lack of “hardware”, i.e. lab equipment, computers, etc. (I05-SL, I06, SL, I07-SL, I08, SL, I10-SL, I13-SL, I14-SL, I15-SL, I18-SL). If e.g. students are trained to apply ITC-skills, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking in hands-on exercises and lab experiments, this is difficult if computers and lab equipment are missing or completely outdated. While it is explicitly beyond the scope of SPHEIR to fund such “hardware”, it is feasible that other programs might be more suitable to this task.

10. Appendix

10.1 Abbreviations

AQHed-SL	Assuring Quality Higher Education in Sierra Leone
AR	Annual Report
BC	British Council
COMAHS	College of Medicine and Allied Health Sciences (at USL)
EBKUST	Ernest Bai Koroma University of Science and Technology (SL)
EPK	Eastern Polytechnic Kenema (SL)
FBC	Fourah Bay College (at USL)
FM	Fund Manager
FR	Framework Reports
FTC	Freetown Teacher's College (Sierra Leone)
GS1	Grant Stage 1
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IQA	Internal Quality Assurance
LMS	Learning Management System
LR	Logframe Reports
MEL	Monitoring, evaluation and learning
MMCET	Milton Margai College of Education and Technology (Sierra Leone)
MPR	Mid-Point Review
MR	Milestone Reports
NU	Njala University (Sierra Leone)
OBE	Outcome-based Education
PMB	Project Management Board
QR	Quarterly Reports
SDN	Skills Development Network
SL	Sierra Leone
SPHEIR	Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education Innovation and Reform
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TVET	Technical Vocational Education and Training
TWG	Technical Working Group
UniMAK	The University of Makeni (Sierra Leone)
USL	University of Sierra Leone (Sierra Leone)
WP	Work Package

10.2 Standardized Quarter Count Identifiers

Although not consistently used across project documents, this report uses the standardized quarter count identifiers for the entire SPHEIR program (see table below). Highlighted is the de-facto run-time for both projects covered by the documentation, which formed the basis for the inception report. A lighter shade indicates the proposed further runtime of both projects. Note that both projects de facto started one quarter later than originally planned.

	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Grant Stage
2017	Q01	Q02	Q03	Q04	Call / 1
2018	Q05	Q06	Q07	Q08	2
2019	Q09	Q10	Q11	Q12	2
2020	Q13	Q14	Q15	Q16	MPR / 3
2021	Q17	Q18	Q19	Q20	3

10.3 Field Interviews Sierra Leone, Field Trip 27 – 31 Jan 2020

ID	Session / Name & Position of Interview Partner	Timing, Format
PS-SL	Common Presentation Session	28 Jan, 90 min, PPT + Q&A
I01-SL	Fatou Taqi, President 50/50 Group	28 Jan, 60 min, 3 group members
I02-SL	Samuel Weekes, Project Director (USL)	28 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I03-SL	Hannah Lewis, Stakeholder Engagement Lead (UMak)	28 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I04-SL	Badamasi Savage, CR Lead (USL - FBC)	28 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I05-SL	Samba Sesay (STEM Lead, USL FBC)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I06-SL	David Caulker (STEM lecturer, USL FBC)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I07-SL	Sulayman Mansaray (STEM Waterfalling Institution, Eastern Polytechnic)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I08-SL	Joseph Edem-Hotah (Health Cluster Lead, USL – COMAHS)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I09-SL	Mohammed Bawoh (Dean Pharamceutical Sciences, USL – COMAHS)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I10-SL	Manso Koroma (Waterfalling Institution, EBKUST; partner to COMAHS)	29 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I11-SL	Jonas Redwood-Sawyer (PMB, USL FBC)	29 Jan, dinner, with Savage
I12-SL	Santigie Kaba/Hannah Lewis (New Management Cluster Lead, UniMak)	30 Jan, 60 min, two-on-one
I13-SL	Sanpha Kallon (Agriculture Cluster Lead, Njala U)	30 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I14-SL	Alie Kamara (Agriculture lecturer, Njala U)	30 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I15-SL	Max Kiambi (Waterfalling-Institution, MMCET)	30 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I16-SL	Ronnie Frazier Williams (QA Lead, Exec Sec, TEC)	30 Jan, 45 min, one-on-one
I17-SL	Suzanne Thomas (KCL-Partner for Health Cluster, COMAHS)	31 Jan, 60 min, with Lush (MEL)
I18-SL	Mable Bangur (Former Student, Agriculture, Njala University)	31 Jan, 45 min, one-on-one
I19-SL	James Cobba (STEM Stakeholder, Ministry of Information and Communication)	31 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one
I20-SL	Ishmael Kamara (Regional Manager, NRA)	31 Jan, 30 min, phone call
I21-SL	Moses Batema (Deputy Managing Director National Medical Supplies Agency)	31 Jan, 60 min, one-on-one